

Dr Dragana Ćorić,
Docent,
Pravni fakultet Univerziteta u Novom Sadu,
Pokrajinski zaštitinik građana-ombudsman,
Republika Srbija

UDK: 341.231.14-053.2(100)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17811893

ČIJA SU ODGOVORNOST PRAVA DETETA? (KONVENCIJA O PRAVIMA DETETA NAKON 35 GODINA POSTOJANJA)

Stav da je Konvencija o pravima deteta donela deci samo prava a ne i obaveze ili odgovornosti je potpuno pogrešan. Deci su priznata prava kao vid njihove zaštite od eksploatacije, nasilja, zanemarivanja i nasilja različitih vidova. Korpusom prava iz pomenute Konvencije deci je priznato ono što ona zapravo imaju od momenta začeca - da su ljudska bića, vredna samim tim što postoje, bez obzira što nisu zbog svojih godina starosti podobna da budu glasači, oni koji plaćaju poreze, zarađuju itd. No da li deca treba da budu sama odgovorna za sopstvena prava i njihovu realizaciju i zaštitu, ili to treba da čine samo odrasli, ili je to treba da bude rezultat zajedničkog truda? U analizi koja će biti urađena u ovom radu, autor će prikazati kako su pojedina neadekvatna tumačenja nekih odredbi Konvencije o pravima deteta izvesna prava deteta dovela do apsurdā (pravo na veroispovest, pravo na izražavanje mišljenja i druga) i ozbiljnim zloupotrebama istih tih prava dovela u opasnost i decu, njihov štit u vidu prava iz imenovane Konvencije i izazvale suprotan efekat od očekivanog.

Ključne reči: prava deteta, odgovornost, tumačenje prava.

Dragana Ćorić, LL.D.,
Assistant Professor,
Faculty of Law, University of Novi Sad,
Ombudsman for the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina,
Republic of Serbia

***WHOSE RESPONSIBILITY ARE CHILDREN'S RIGHTS?
(THE CONVENTION ON THE RIGHTS OF THE
CHILD 35 YEARS AFTER ADOPTION)***

The view that the Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) only grants children rights and no obligations or responsibilities is utterly wrong. Children's rights have been recognized as a form of ensuring their protection from various kinds of exploitation, violence, neglect and abuse. The corpus of rights envisaged in the Convention recognizes the inalienable right which children actually have from the moment of conception: that they are human beings, valuable by their existence per se, and despite the fact that they are not eligible to vote, pay taxes, earn money (etc.) due to their age. Yet, should children be responsible for their own rights, their exercise and protection, or should this be done only by adults? Or, should it be the result of joint efforts? In the analysis provided in this paper, the author will show how inadequate interpretations of individual CRC provisions have contributed to making certain rights of the child absurd (e.g. the right to religion, the right to express opinion, etc.) and put children in danger as a result of serious abuses of these rights. Thus, instead of being the shield of children's rights guaranteed under the Convention, these interpretations have caused the opposite effect.

Keywords: children's rights, responsibility, interpretation of law.